

APPLICATION OF DECISION THEORY IN THE SELECTION OF ELECTRIC CHARGING STATIONS FOR AN SME

Georgiana BORZ ¹, Livia FILIP ² Adrian PÎSLĂ ³
PhD Student¹, PhD Student², Prof. PhD³
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania
borzgeorgiana98@yahoo.com ¹, livia.filip@staff.utcluj.ro ², adrian.pisla@muri.utcluj.ro ³
<http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – The research considers the application of decision theory in the selection process of the electric charging station, dedicated to inclusion in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), aiming at behavioral modeling and the advantages of an SME in the use of electric vehicles. The integration of electric vehicles (EVs) into the transportation ecosystem has required the development of a strategic framework for the selection of electric charging stations, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that want to increase their sustainability and operational efficiency thus the study exploring the application of theory decision in the selection process of electric charging stations for SMEs, emphasizing the importance of a structured approach in optimizing both economic and environmental results.

Methodology/approach – Detail the decision theory based on questioning the necessity, defining the purpose and clearly stating the advantages based on hypothesis and organization data collection. The critical interpretation is partially eclectic, using also recognized applied methodologies. Using principles of decision theory, the research develops a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) model to evaluate various charging station options based on factors such as cost, location, accessibility and technological compatibility. By applying quantitative methods to evaluate these criteria, the study aims to provide SMEs with a robust decision-making framework that balances operational needs with sustainability goals.

Findings – A reconsidered view about the charging systems, including the accumulators, type of chargers' source of electricity and the potential environmental impact.

Research limitations/implications – Some hypothesis and finding testing must be continued, was difficult to report at this stage of the research, due to resources limitations and the pandemic and post-pandemic encloser and impact over a proper statistical analysis.

Practical implications – A new and adequate approach for inducing electromobility in SMEs, for employees and freight transport, thus generating a comprehensive approach to the trade-offs involved in selecting electric charging stations, providing practical insights for SMEs looking to make informed and strategic investment decisions in electric mobility.

Originality/value – A practical view over the resource's investment and advantages of electric mobility.

Key words: SME, Electromobility, Charging stations.

Introduction

Lately mobility and especially individual mobility has gone through many transformations. The battle on market shares is divided between Battery-Electric, Plug-in-Hybrid, Hybrid Electric, Fuel Cell Electric, LPG, Ethanol E85, other fuels and the classical Petrol and Diesel ones.

Many discussions end in 2024 to the conclusion that in spite of the increase of the battery performance and decrease the Battery Electric cars price, the EU market remains constant slowing down the heavy increase of the former years. The only company in the TOP15 manufacturers that increase sell, but without changing the position is Toyota.

Car sales have shown mixed trends across the EU, in part due to diverging policies on green incentives. The performance development and implementation of the charging station is directly influenced by the number of users, the trend of EV implementation and the reached % of the total market.

A strong example in this sense is the business model of Europe's largest platform for consumers, the Octopus Energy's electric vehicle (EV) charging platform. With nearly 850,000 connected chargers, targeting this year the 1 million users' market, the No1 in Europe accelerates the worldwide presence.

Drivers can access Octopus Energy charging platform in 40 countries, available in 20 languages. With one tap, can be accessed one of the 80% of the chargers on Europe's public charging network.

Launched 4 years ago, in the summer of 2020, Octopus Electroverse is the answer to the frequent driver's complaint that many apps and cards are needed to use the so many different brands of EV charging stations.

So, the free-to-use app across Europe, from Octopus Electroverse expanded by integrating 950 charge point brands, among which are identified Aral Pulse, Charge Place Scotland, Free To X, InstaVolt, IONITY, Osprey, MFG, Powerdot, or TotalEnergies.

From the other side of the ocean, in the USA, the state of California has surpassed 150,000 chargers installed statewide. From that almost 10% are fast chargers. The building of a better and bigger charging network is a key part of the California Governor's agenda for delivering infrastructure upgrades across the entire state. For the achievement of these plans cannot be ignored the California expectation to receive more than \$380 million from the President Biden's Bipartisan Infrastructure Law, dedicated to building out chargers, after this year 1 billion funding approved for EV charging and hydrogen refueling projects for cars, trucks, and buses.

So, the actual picture of the California electric vehicles chargers (EVC) looks like in the following picture:

Electric Vehicle Chargers in California

As of August 2024

Figure 1. The California electric vehicles chargers' evolution

Looking at the local market, the purpose of the study is to apply the theory in the selection decision for electric charging station within SMEs, combined with the possibility to orient doctoral studies, aiming to have a direct use of the decision modeling implementation. By utilizing decision theory, the study provides a structured framework to make informed choices, even in complex environments.

The research explores the application of decision theory in selecting electric charging stations for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The goal is to guide SMEs through the process of decision modeling, helping them navigate the trade-offs and considerations involved in making the most suitable and profitable choices when selecting charging stations, with emphasis on practical implementation, ensuring that SMEs can adopt strategic and well-informed investment decisions that align with their operational and sustainability objectives.

SMEs attitude

The SMEs are generally dynamic economic units but within limited resources, especially in the early stage.

The dynamic component of a SME represents an advantage for large acceptance of innovation and new trends. Here is included also the electro mobility, acquisition and use. As a relatively new technology, it is still expensive, the continuous evolution and the intended mass production, together with larger companies' implication and governmental facilities, the trend is to diminish the price. China plays a crucial role in price reduction by promoting the 10.000 Euro models.

Within EU, the necessity to use EVs for business and ensure the climate change effects reduction is very much connected also with the distribution of the chargers' network and the sources of electricity, in the current research we are advocating also for the green electricity.

The Theory Components

The Decision Theory is a branch of decision sciences that studies the decision-making process under conditions of uncertainty, risk, and conflict of interest. These address how people make decisions and how their decisions can be evaluated in terms of efficiency, rationality, and consequences [Kahneman, (2011); Peterson, (2009)].

The Decision Theory has applications in a variety of fields, including business, economics, engineering, psychology, public policy, and more. It provides tools for optimizing the outcomes under diverse conditions [Gibbons, (1992)]. In this context “the decision” refers to the choice or selection of a particular option from a set of available alternatives. The decision is the result of a deliberate and rational process in which an individual or group analyzes the relevant information, evaluates the risks and benefits associated with each option, and selects the one considered the most suitable or efficient according to the established objectives.

The decision can be influenced by various factors such as available knowledge, individual preferences, risk tolerance, time constraints and social pressures. Decision theory explores how these elements affect the decision – making process and how people can make decisions under conditions of uncertainty or risk. This approach also looks at the degree of rationality in decision-making, recognizing that factors such as cognitive biases or emotional influences can intervene in the process of thought and choice.

The study of decision theory aims to enhance decision-making quality by employing models, game theories, and other analytical techniques [Tversky and Kahneman, (1974); Keeney and Raiffa, (1993)]. An analytical tool that can be utilized in the context of electric charging stations and SMEs is Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). This analysis can be used to evaluate various locations or types of charging stations. The criteria may include cost, anticipated usage of the charging stations, environmental impact, and installation time. By assigning scores and weights to these criteria, decision-makers can systematically compare and identify the most advantageous options for investing in the locations or types of charging stations for the SME.

Key aspects of decision theory are decision modelling which is related to understanding how individuals or groups make decisions. This involves the analysis of factors that influence the decision-making process, such as available information, individual preferences, cognitive and emotional limitations. Risk and uncertainty are related to decision theory dealing with situations where the outcome of a decision is uncertain or there is a degree of risk associated with it. This includes the identification and assessment of risks and how people manage this uncertainty in decision-making. Optimization and rationality are referring to the analysis of how decisions can be evaluated from the perspective of optimization, more exactly, finding the best possible solution according to specific criteria. Decision theory explores and analyzes how people make decisions and examines the extent to which people make rational decisions or whether they are affected by cognitive biases or other influences [Saca, Victor and Oleg, (2013)].

Formulation of the decision-making problem, clearly establishing the nature of the problem or opportunity that requires a decision is the initial most important activity. This implies the correct definition of the situation [Saca, Victor and Oleg, (2013)]. The multitude of variants is the result of the developing process to identify a set of possible alternatives to address the problem or take advantage of an opportunity [Saca, Victor and Oleg, (2013)].

The elements of the decision-making process within decision theory are particularly considered for the electromobility i.e. the charging station implementation by following a list of definitions that creates a sort of guidance limits in the decision process.

The **objectives of the decision** are clearly defining the goals and objectives that the decision must achieve. This provides a framework for evaluating options [Klößner, (2014)], being crucial aspects of the decision-making process, and their awareness, proper management contribute to informed and effective decision-making.

The **states of objective conditions** (states of nature) are elements to be identified as possible states of nature or objective conditions that can influence the outcome of the decision [Klößner, (2014)]. The decision maker is the person or group making the decision. The decision maker can be a single person, a team or an organization [Saca, Victor and Oleg, (2013)].

An important part of the decision is if game theory is considered. Game theory deals with the strategic interactions between different parties involved in decision making. It looks at how one party's choices can influence outcomes for other parties involved. The decision evaluation can be made by comparing associated costs and benefits. This involves evaluating the pros and cons of each available option to make informed decisions [Keeney and Raiffa, (1993)].

In Decision theory can be classified the types of decisions in a way that addresses the specific methods and models for each type. Regarding the classification of decisions there are: **programmed decisions** which are structured, repetitive and routine decisions. Both are taken in common situations and can be easily managed by a set of procedures. **Routine decisions** are taken regularly, without requiring extensive analysis. Non-routine decisions are not made frequently, are more complex and require more careful analysis. **Unscheduled decisions** that are more complex and less structured decisions that require more analysis and evaluation. They occur in less common and not clear information [Berar, (2000)].

Individual decisions are taken by a single person, who analyzes and decides on the situation. Group decisions are made by a group of people working together to reach a consensus or a collective decision [Berar, (2000)].

The operational decisions are taken at the basic level of the organization and are related to day-to-day activities. **The tactical decisions** are taken at the intermediate level of the organization and refer to how strategic decisions are implemented. **The strategic decisions** are taken at the highest level of the organization and affect the general direction and its long-term objectives [Berar, (2000)].

Certain decisions are based on clear information and the results can be known from the beginning. **Risky decisions** are related to a certain degree of uncertainty about the outcomes, but the probabilities associated with them can be estimated.

Uncertain decisions represent a limited amount of information and expected outcomes, their associated probabilities to occur are unknown [Berar, (2000)].

The set of criteria for evaluating the variants is transformed into a clear and relevant list of selected criteria for evaluating and comparing available options. The set of consequences of the criteria for evaluating the variants, evaluating the consequences of each option against established criteria to determine the impact and benefits of each choice [Saca, Victor and Oleg, (2013)].

Type of criteria:

Bayes-Laplace criterion (equal probabilities) is based on probabilities and assumes that the decision maker can estimate probabilities of different possible outcomes of a decision. The probability assigned to the maximum result is chosen [Rebelo, et al., (2016)].

Hurwicz's criterion (optimistic): tries to find a balance between an optimistic and pessimistic approach. Multiply the maximum possible values of a result by a constant ($0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$) and the minimum value by $(1-\alpha)$.

Wald's criterion (pessimistic) is also known as "maximin", involves choosing the option that maximizes the minimum possible outcomes. It is a more pessimistic approach, where the decision maker tries to minimize the maximum risk [Rebelo, et al., (2016)].

Savage's Criterion (regrets): is also known as „minimax regret" and is based on the idea of regret. The decision maker considers the possible losses associated with each option that minimizes the maximum possible regret [Rebelo, et al., (2016)].

Each of these criteria reflects different approaches to risk, uncertainty and decision-maker preferences in the process. The use of a particular criterion may depend on the specific context of the decision and the individual preferences of the decision maker [Rocha et al., (2007)].

The advantage of decision theory is the structured decision-making process on which theory provides a framework and set of tools to structure and formalize the decision-making process. This can facilitate a more systematic and clear approach to problems adding the mathematical rigor basis for decision analysis.

Related to identifying risks and consequences the decision theory helps in identifying and evaluating the risks associated with different options as well as evaluating their consequences. This can lead to more informed decisions, the flexible approach, the various methods and criteria allowing the theory adaptation to different contexts and individual preferences.

The disadvantages of decision theory are the oversimplification when some models and methods in decision theory can oversimplify complex real-world situations, ignoring important and nuanced aspects:

- The unrealistic assumptions on which some theories and models considers that decision makers have perfect knowledge for an accurate assess of the probabilities and consequences of each option.
- Lack of adaptability to human behavior: some criticism claim that decision theory does not take enough account of the emotional, irrational and social aspects of human decision-making.
- Mismatch in cases of extreme uncertainty in the case of decisions made under conditions of extreme uncertainty or in very complex decision situations, decision theory may provide limited guidance or not flexible enough.

Annually, a report on electric mobility is produced by the Roland Berger global consulting company. Romania being one of the target markets in the 6th edition of the "Romania E-Mobility Index" study shows that the growth rate of plug-in hybrid (PHEV) vehicle registrations being at high altitudes. Thanks to a 70% increase in EV and PHEV registrations, Romania succeeded in 2022 for the first time to surpass countries such as Italy or Spain, having a 12% from the new car registrations, when Spain indicates 10% and Italy 9%.

In addition to these performances of ERV and PHEV vehicles, is considered also the situation of the charging stations. As a rule, is an approach of insufficient increase in the number electric charging stations. In 2022 were 1,350 stations in Romania, 58% (785) are of 22 kW AC type, 40% (540) above 22kWAC up to 150kW DC, and 2% (25) ultrafast, above 150kW. In 2024 are already over 5000 charging stations.

On an amount up to 30% of cases, the charging station can be already found in the shopping centers area, in 2022 the number increased 374 from 270 in 2021, mostly with fast or ultrafast loading DC loading systems. One of the biggest increases was in the gas stations area, existing about 3000 in Romania in 2024, so at the end of the year, from the new 164 new charging station 74% (121) was of fast type.

The car dealers contribute to the increased number of charging stations, by creating a direct pressure or true the increased number of EV sold, but also by delivering some models with an included charging station.

Already from 2020, Roland Berger offers an important detail that EVs end up equaling the thermal engine after approximately 8,000 km traveled. According to Roland Berger's reports, this point of equilibrium is because the CO₂ emissions saved by using an electric vehicle equal the pollution generated from its production, including the production of the batteries used by electric vehicles. This study also emphasizes the importance of transitioning to renewable energy sources for charging electric vehicles, thereby maximizing the environmental benefits. Depending on the energy mix required for vehicle production, electricity, and the vehicle's efficiency, this point of equilibrium can vary. However, an approximation suggests a value around 8,000 kilometers driven, establishing a general threshold [(Berger, R. et al., 2015)].

Connection with development of doctoral studies in the technical field

The approach of different topics depends on the “forces” that are requesting of considering the studies. If the social component, the public, the population needs to be informed in an as neutral manner as possible then we must consider the doctoral studies as the most appropriate to identify a viable model that demonstrate the dimension of a problem at the possibilities in solving it. Doctoral journey is not only about gaining and disseminate knowledge, but also about building relationships and joining prestigious specialists, universities collaborating with international institutions, allowing the engagement with a global community of experts, that may become pivotal connections, opening doors to collaborative research projects.

In this category is entering also the application of the Decision Theory, especially because is addressed to the important problem of climate change that impose a lot of ideas and regulations, not all useful, not all scientifically based or sustainable having in site only o short period of time or a narrow horizon. Electromobility benefits from populist support. In the selection and operation of the EVs and the electric charging stations there are not really green solutions, but the most pecuniary elements are in the front.

Due to the doctoral studies, endorsement for green, sustainable and end users' money efficient solution the acquisition, the placement, and operation of the charging stations will promote real green electricity for EV using, based on scientific validated results. Especially due to apparently contradictory data and information from the considered reliable sources.

Based on the doctoral studies that we are advocating, the contradiction appears from the geopolitical different situations, the biggest player being Europe, USA, China, Rusia and India, followed emergent countries.

China, Rusia and India are playing a double role due to the large regional development discrepancies. In the present and future studies, we will focus on the Europe – USA and the others impact on this connection, China, Rusia and India are not to be ignored.

An analysis from the USA Department of Energy by Bloomberg Green estimates the number of fast-charging public sites will be greater than gas stations by 2030 if the current pace continues. In 2024 is expected that operators will double their 2023 investment to reach a collective \$6.1 billion (Full Story: Bloomberg 7/18). Only in Q2 of 20204 were added about 700 new public fast-charging stations for electric cars in the second quarter, bringing the nationwide total to nearly 9,000. But the US greenhouse gas emissions are not falling fast enough, So, they will not meet the Biden administration's goal of cutting greenhouse gas pollution by at least half in 2030, compared with 2005 levels, according to new analysis by research firm Rhodium Group.

From sources across the web

Figure 2. List of the emergent countries, players in the environmental impact reduction and promotion of the electromobility

The Inflation Reduction Act, passed in 2022, has helped create a pathway for deep decarbonization across the energy and transportation sectors – but the US is still only on track to achieve as much as a 43% emissions reduction at the start of the next decade, the unexpected reality is that the skyrocketing electricity demand from artificial intelligence and other data center uses as one of the key obstacles. And in this market, electricity and especially green electricity demand, is playing also the electromobility.

This kind of news came just days after (July 2024) new figures indicated that China, as the world's biggest polluter seconded by the USA, have peaked its output of greenhouse gases in 2023. Only a rapid pace of emissions reductions in China and the US, would play a critical role in meeting the Paris Agreement's goal of limiting planetary warming to below 2C above the pre-industrial average, and ideally to 1.5C. But the latest evolutions shown that is hardly to believe that with no China commitment and US's commitment to the agreement, the Biden administration pledged the country will achieve net zero emissions no later than 2050, is contradicted by the current trajectory to 2030, the country is off track for this mid-century goal, in spite of some recorded progress in emissions reductions that fell (as the economy expanded) with 1.9% year-over-year, in 2023 being recorded 18% lower than they were in 2005, but they raised in the two years before, after the pandemic drawbacks.

The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) makes historic investments in climate action that are expected to reduce U.S. emissions ~40% by 2030 while supporting disadvantaged communities and the clean energy industrial base, but the passage of the IRA has also made further cuts look more likely as it supports the expansion of wind, solar and electric vehicles. An estimate of energy and transportation emissions in the U.S. is presented in Figure 2, showing a significant decrease in these emissions across various sectors such as transportation, industry, power, buildings, and agriculture.

US Power and Transport Emissions Are Projected to Fall Significantly

Measured in net million metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalent

Figure 3. An estimate of energy and transportation emissions in the U.S. through 2035

The zero-emitting sources like wind, solar and **nuclear** could account for 62-88% of total electricity generation in 2035, due to support from IRA subsidies and new Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) limits for power plant emissions, depending on how quickly cleaner power generators can be built to match growing electricity demand from EVs and data centers.

The doctoral studies advocating electromobility are sustained by the capacity of transportation sector emissions to decrease by 25-35%, aided by stringent EPA standards for vehicles, the studies made by the Rhodium Group, as an independent research provider, combining policy expertise and data-driven analysis to help decision-makers navigate global challenges, sees EVs representing as much as 74% of light-duty vehicle sales by 2032, but a lot could change depending on the results of elections in November, a win for former President Donald Trump might lead to policy rollbacks.

This kind of statements from USA” by 2030 the number of charging station will exceed the number of gas stations” seems to be considered differently in EU, and as mentioned are obsolete in Romania, had existed a ratio of 5 to 3 in the favor of charge stations. It is true that under 50% of these are fast chargers and the actual distribution is not offering the expected satisfaction, because their type, placement, access and waiting times are not creating a synergy of charging facility.

Therefore, the doctoral studies orientation is also a research topic, the actual our doctoral research revealing that the development of PhD students’ skills is as important as the research carried on by the PhD student and that the interdisciplinary approach of the research will offer greater benefits for the student and the student results. Pursuing these concepts, doctoral studies can have a stronger positive impact on the research field and on society, generating new insights, solutions, and innovations. Sharing the new gained e your knowledge, contribute to the development of knowledge, policy, practice, and technological culture.

Discussion and conclusions

US will miss Biden's ambitious 2030 goal for cutting pollution

SMEs' adaptability and receptiveness to new technologies enable them to implement electromobility despite ongoing budget constraints and technological hurdles. The need for green energy, technological advancements, and government incentives—particularly from China and the EU—are expected to lower electric vehicle prices, increasing public confidence in transitioning from conventional to electric vehicles. While Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) and Decision Theory may sometimes oversimplify complex real-world scenarios and human dynamics, they provide SMEs with structured tools to evaluate investment opportunities. Despite the notable expansion of charging infrastructure, challenges related to distribution and charger types persist. Policy developments such as the U.S. Inflation Reduction Act and global perspectives on electric transportation highlight the importance of integrating green solutions and adapting to regional variations. Doctoral research may offer better and honest solutions, different from media marketing. Electromobility can be green and sustainable and can reduce the climate impact if it is used in an appropriate manner, and the source of electricity is green. The charging stations can make a difference in the exploitation of the EVs and the way in which will be largely and efficient adopted from personal locomotion system to large freight transports, the smart component of the electric charging station leading to money and time saving, together with the CO2 footprint reduction.

References

Kahneman, D.

2011

"Thinking, Fast and Slow." Farrar, Straus and Giroux.

Peterson, M.

2009

"An Introduction to Decision Theory." Cambridge University Press

Gibbons, R.

1992

"An Introduction to Decision Theory." Cambridge University Press.

Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D.

1974

"Judgment under Uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases." *Science*, 185(4157), 1124-1131.

Keeney, R. L., & Raiffa, H.

1993

"Decisions with Multiple Objectives: Preferences and Value Trade-Offs." Cambridge University Press.

Saca, Victor, and Oleg Solomon.

2013

"Structural Elements of the Decision-Making Process: Analytical Reflections."

Lungu, F.

2023

„Quantitative Analysis“-course support.

Klößner, Christian A.

2014

"The dynamics of purchasing an electric vehicle—A prospective longitudinal study of the decision-making process."

Berar, S.

"The Decision-Making System of the company: Economic and Informatic Perspectives."

2000

Rebelo, M. F., Santos, G., & Silva, R.

2016

"Integration of management systems: towards a sustained success and development of organizations".

Rocha, M., Searcy, C., & Karapetrovic, S.

2007

"Integrating sustainable development into existing management systems".

Berger, R. et al.

2015

"Fuel Cell Electric Buses: Potential for Sustainable Public Transport in Europe".